

PastModern Modular

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Abstract.

In this paper, we discuss the possibility of duplication of certain historical music instruments in virtual reality as interactive digital twins, initially for the purpose of cultural preservation. We then suggest taking this concept one step further by integrating them into a modular system. Furthermore we apply mereotopological thinking and propose the possibility of modularity of higher degrees of freedom. We provide a philosophical and conceptual basis for this research, showing a wider perspective of changes in time and space perception, and illustrate our argument with speculative sketches and a proof of concept prototype, utilizing one of procedural audio techniques in the Unity3D engine, working with Meta Quest 2 VR controller.

Keywords: Virtual Reality Music Instruments (VRMI), media archeology, mereotopology, procedural audio, modularity, time travel, eternal life.

1 Introduction: Reassembling the Spatiotemporal

1.1 Media Archeology of Sonic Incriptions

This project is inspired by the media archeological view on technological phenomena as subjects of cultural significance, which not only should be preserved and studied, but also researched for discovering new perspectives.

Field of Media Archeology originated on the border between the 20s and 21st century, with the term coined by Siegfried Zielinski (Zielinski 2002) first in German and elaborated in further publications by other authors internationally (Huntamo 2011, Parikka 2012). Our focus is on music technology, which we suggest to view as a type of sonic inscription (Magnusson 2019).

In recent decades a lot of projects have appeared, which were reviving sound devices from the past. Examples can be publications and series of exhibitions by Andrey Smirnov about the sound and music experiments of Soviet Era Russia (Smirnov 2013), or numerous recreations of Russolo's *Intonarumori*: either rigorous and precise (Chessa 2012) or more freely interpretive (Suzuki 2013) (see Fig.1). Perhaps the modern movement of Eurorack and Buchla modular synthesizers revival - is one of the most obvious examples of how the

media archeological paradigm is present in popular music culture. But there are many more.

Fig. 1. Left: Intonarumori instruments built by Russolo and Ugo Piatti circa 1910, photo published in Russolo's 1913 book "The Art of Noises" and here taken from (Russolo 1986). Right: Composer Luciano Chessa conducting The Orchestra of Futurist Noise Intoners (one of Intonarumori reproductions) in 2023, here taken from (Opening concert 2023).

In the last 20 years electronic music in general became a part of mass culture. Subsequently, more and more people are interested in its history. Sadly, a lot of early electronic music instruments (EMIs) were lost, scrapped and forgotten. At the same time, even the famous Musical Instruments Museum in Brussels features some very unique EMIs in its permanent collection - thus the cultural necessity of preserving these objects is no doubt.

But preservation of time and space becomes easier as the techniques of modeling objects and recording and storing information upgrade and become more affordable. That's why modernistic linear spatio-temporal projections can be questioned. We can argue that in the digital era we sometimes should approach time differently.

1.2 Disjunction of spatio-temporality and why we can travel in time

The term "temporal disjunction" is associated with the work of the French philosopher Gilles Deleuze. Deleuze is known for his exploration of time, particularly in his book "Difference and Repetition" (Deleuze 1994) and his collaborations with Félix Guattari, such as "A Thousand Plateaus." In these works, Deleuze investigates the complex nature of time and argues that it is not a linear progression but rather a multiplicity of divergent temporalities.

Temporal disjunction in Deleuze's philosophy encompasses various concepts, including the idea of the "virtual" as a realm of potentiality that disrupts linear time, the notion of "becoming" as a process of continual change and transformation, and the concept of "rhizomatic" structures that resist hierarchical organization.

Indeed in our everyday culture we may experience examples of how progression of media and digital memory lead to parallel timing. One of many illustrations can be subcultures of historical fashion, or medieval religious rituals, or technologies from the 19th century

coming back on market in the form of start-ups (e.g. Camera Lucida from 1806 returning on market in 2013 as NeoLucida startup).

Perhaps one of the most interesting - is the variety of “mild traditionalist” in Mark Sedgwick’s terms (Sedgwick 2009) movements of modern young people deliberately choosing to live in different times (see Fig.2). Same as with historical technologies - these types of performative lives became possible (sustainable and enjoyable) for these people thanks to the evolution of media and progress of society and culture. In other words, a 35 y.o. person in modern New York City can dress and partly live like in the 19th century, because he had easy access to very detailed information about that time (via the internet), including dress patterns and materials. But also he had access to modern productions, supply chains and all other mediated technologies (including digital financial transactions), which made it possible for him to partly recreate a lifestyle from another era. Last but not least, he finds himself in a social situation, where such an obvious deviation from aesthetic conformity is not punished, due to the general evolution of western societies towards some level of tolerance. And that evolution might also be a derivation of technical progress and developments of modern media (Miller 2013).

We can say that the way this young man dresses at some point in history became impractical and went out of fashion - the conditions for it to be sustainable have disappeared. But, after 200 years - some other conditions appeared - and a similar lifestyle became possible.

Fig. 2. Left: Zack MacLeod Pinsent (35 y.o.) in 2019 dresses as a British Regency gentleman every day (source: BBC News). Center: Sarah and Gabriel Chrisman in 2019 wear 1880s-inspired clothing, cook with a wood stove and live their everyday lives, in Port Townsend, Washington, as if it's the 19th century (source: New York Post). Right: Ben Sansum (35 y.o.) in 2014, but he lived in 1946. Here he demonstrated his dry non-flushable toilet exactly like it was in the 40s (source: BBC News).

The analogy to this historical trajectory in the world of music technology can be found for example in a relatively new instrument called Glissotar (Glissonic Tarogato), an international marketing for which has started circa 2023. It is a woodwind instrument, which realizes an idea similar to the one of slide saxophone developed in the early 20's century (see Fig.3). But Glissotar uses a bunch of modern technologies (like digital modeling and fabrication) and materials (magnetic flexible stripes), which make the

engineering more elegant and economically efficient. We see that after 100 years some conditions emerged for the idea to re-appear, following similar aesthetics, but on another technical level.

Fig. 3. Up: Slide Saxophone, c. 1922 by Reiffel & Husted (Museum of Making Music, California). (source: Wikipedia). Down: Glissotar, c. 2023 (source: www.glissonic.com).

The extensive discussion on temporal disjunction is out of scope of this paper. For us it is important to stress that this is one of the features of modern existence, which probably will progress more, as the technologies of recording, storage and modeling with digital data will evolve.

But what is the near future in this regard? We suggest that a simple extrapolation of modern trends can lead us to a very specific possibility of time travel (or complete indifference to linearity of time). The one which is not based on quantum physics, but on information. And it is partly possible even now, though we do not perceive it as something special.

1.3 Informational Theory of Time Travel

- 1) As life becomes more digital (we spend more time on the internet) - personal memory becomes more digital (we leave a digital trace).
- 2) Because digital traces are recorded and stored - it is possible to go back in individual time, within the limit of the recorded data.
- 3) If all individual traces could be calculated in relation to each other - it could be possible to go back in collective (cultural) time.
- 4) If all individual traces could be recalculated in relation to each other in real-time - it could be possible to constantly change the collective past.

A Past-Time recalculated in Real-Time becomes a Past-in-Real-Time.

Examples of the limited time travel to the past - are scrolling behaviors in social networks, when we check our posts from years ago and what other people commented. The big

difference between this and checking family photo albums, is that we have recordings of how other people behaved in relation to our post and we immediately can go to their profile and see what was happening with them at that moment.

The extrapolation of this to step 5 would be - an edit of the post from years ago, with subsequent edits of all records of related behaviors of others. We may suggest that at least some elements of this speculative theory will be applied in our everyday lives in future. And it will be more immersive, then just reading text messages or watching photos. The more of a physical space will be recorded and modeled inside digital spaces - the more immersive this type of temporal disjunction will be. This specific view on time leads us to a certain way of dealing with space. We call it mereotopological perspective.

1.4 Mereology and mereotopology: question of whole and parts

The focus of this work is music technology. So far we expressed the cultural need in preservation of unique technologic music objects. Then we outlined the global condition of temporal disjunction, which is based on digitalization and in our view may progress in future up to complete indifference to a linearity of time. One of the basis for this conjecture - is digitalization and storage of physical spaces, including objects in it. Including musical objects like instruments.

We approached time from the perspective of temporal disjunction. Now we approach space from the view of mereology.

In simple terms - mereology is a philosophical concern with whole and parts and their interrelations. Mereotopology - is a formal instrumentalization of mereology. It suggests the possibility of alternative calculuses, aside from point-based geometries. For example, a region-based calculus. It is for sure out of scope of this text to go into much detail about these subjects and we can refer readers to (Cotnoir & Varzi 2021) and (Stell 2017).

Our mereological argument is that a real musical instrument, existing in a physical space as an object - is complex and consists of parts. But the level of complexity (number of parts) really depends on the person who approaches this object. It seems like the essence of a musical instrument is to be used to play music. But this is mostly true for a musician. For an engineer - the instrument is a collection of different modules. For a designer - it is an interesting part of an interior, which may have a volume. For a historian of art - it is a decoration, related to some period in time. For a historian of technology - it is a collection of parts, each of which stores an ontological information about some period in history. And so on. So when we approach a digitalization (a recording in a form of modeling) of a musical instrument - we have to be concerned with what level of detail we will be proceeding with. What number and kinds of parts will constitute the whole of the object.

The ideal situation will require as much detail as possible, but in reality we will have to work with limited computational power and limited storage.

The digitalization is also directly related to a question of modeling the actual process of generation of sounds. Some of the instruments may combine mechanical and electrical processes. To what level of detail should we model this in virtual 3D space, and what parts can we leave to a pure calculation or even a simulation with imprecise techniques? The example of the latter would be a use of a prerecorded audio samples instead of physical modeling synthesis. Or the use of low resolution mesh instead of photo-realistic textures.

The mereotopological argument - is a possible instrumental solution to the questions above. We divide it into two parts.

First. We accept the limitations and the fact that VR and modeling techniques are in permanent progress themselves. This means that the realization of the project will always be temporary and require constant renovation, along with the growing possibilities of evolving media.

On a level of practical work this can be expressed in metaphorical utilization of so called LOD (Level Of Detail) methodology, which is used inside Unity3D game engine - the platform for the development of proof of concept prototypes for this publication.

Level of detail (LOD) is a technique that reduces the number of GPU operations that Unity requires to render distant meshes. E.g. the further away the object from the viewer in VR space - the less GPU power directed to its render.

In our case, we will be alternating the level of details (number and functionality of parts) depending on various conditions. For example a condition could be the limitations of GPU power of the machine used for prototyping. Or another condition would be - a limitation of time before the deadline for submission for publication. This may result in the existence of different versions of the project.

Second. The prospective idea of this project - a possibility of modularity. This means that at least some of the models should consist of modules as their parts. The main feature of the modules - would be their interconnectivity. This is a simple manifestation of our own module-based mereotopological calculus for this exploration. And because we are creating it - it is possible to add to it some unusual degrees of freedom, which would not be possible in real physical space, but could be modeled in VR.

1.5 On postmodern Cut-Up techniques and Modularity. What is PastModern Modular?

Cut-up - is a creative technique, popularized by artists of all genres in the middle of the 20th century. It is strongly based on the possibility of the medium to be divided, reassembled and glued back together and originates in the Dadaism movement. William Burroughs used to cut-up newspapers and his own texts to glue them into novels, poets like Brion Gysin - combined words with cut and reassembled pre-recorded sounds, Genesis-P-Orridge started cutting and remixing pieces of audio as manifestations of reality itself, and then generalized into their own body and whole ontology. Pierre Schaeffer developed musique concrete based on similar technical principles. And subsequent music sampling and collaging also could be seen as cut-ups (Adema 2017). With time cut-ups began to be strongly associated with postmodernist aesthetics and transgression, with dominance of form and medium over everything else. Cut-up became part of mass culture and western aesthetics. And maybe unsurprisingly we can see similarities between cut-ups and modular synthesis.

Today we can talk about hardware devices or a software interface as a media equal to symbols on a paper - because it is a type of inscription. An object - is information about the object. In media theory this argument perhaps can be attributed to Marshall McLuhan. And in the context of studies of music interfaces to (Magnusson 2019).

Modular synthesizer (or a node-based programming system) - can be seen as a cut-up technique platform for sound construction. We scrape parts of other patches and parts of code and parts of old modules and merge them in between each other. But in the case of modules and nodes - this type of creativity is pre-designed. It is supposed to be. Unlike in other media (text on a paper or audio/video recording, etc.), used in cut-ups.

In our project we think about adding modularity to something, which was not supposed to be modular. Cut-up is a sort of specific mereotopological calculus of its own.

We call it PastModern Modular, because we cut-up elements of past, elements of modern, we recombine these parts into a speculative whole, which resembles a postmodernist recursive play in its concept and realization but also in its name itself.

1.6 Virtual Reality and Digital Twins: framework for standardization and archivation

An experience of working with electronic music production nowadays is unimaginable without the usage of unifying protocols like MIDI, OSC, CV, or line level audio. They eventually allow all of the pieces of equipment to be interconnected. The music production studio is a gunk-whole in a mereological sense. It is an instrument of itself thanks to modularity, which is provided by the standard protocols of signal and data transmission. Another type of standardization easily found in this environment is a uniform of size. The equipment is designed to fit spatially. A lot of it follows the standard of Rack Unit, inherited from telecommunication industries of the early 20s century (supposedly introduced by AT&T in 1922). Others follow a philosophy of table-top operation, either being put on a stand, or a table.

One of the features of early historical EMIs and related experimental instruments - is the lack of these types of standardizations. Some of them were as big as a two store building

(Telharmonium), others were relatively portable, but due to non-existence of line level audio had to rely on dedicated amplification and custom designed speaker systems (early versions of Theremin).

We suggest that Virtual Reality naturally provides a universally standardized environment. In other words - in VR everything can be interconnected on the levels of data transmission and spatial assembly.

Furthermore, VR provides a possibility to preserve information about spatiality relative to the size of a human body and natural degrees of freedom, available for the operations of this body. This means that we not only can archive and store the experience of being near (or inside) the historical object, but we also can preserve the experience of operating with it - something called Interactive Kinematic Concept (IKC) in terms from (Kasich 2023) or Ergographic Agent or the carrier for Ergogenetic Memory in terms from (Magnusson 2019) - a performative DNA of a musical instrument.

Copies of hardware systems in VR are long known in engineering as “Digital Twins”. A lot of practical research has been done in this field (Hehenberger 2016, Grieves 2019). In a wider sense - as copies of real objects and environments - Digital Twins are currently used in all spheres of public life including medicine, archeology, social sciences and many more. And naturally this approach has been used in cultural heritage preservation as shown in (Hutson 2023). Interestingly enough, research suggests that modularity is an essential characteristic of a digital twin (Rosen 2015). This indirectly proves that the possibility of creative practice, based on recombination of modules inside the VR environment consisting of digital twins of real objects (e.g. music instruments) - is a next logical step after fulfilling the purpose of cultural preservation.

1.7 Virtual Reality Music Instruments (VRMIs)

We conclude our conceptualization of PastModern Modular with the necessary mention of a long existing field of Virtual Reality Music Instruments (VRMIs). A lot of artists, scholars and developers have made their contribution to this field over the last decades. Going into much detail on this topic is out of our scope, but a comprehensive state of the art could be found in (Serafin 2016) and (Atherton 2020). And our project is obviously another possibility of application of the VRMI paradigm.

1.8 PastModern Modular

We believe that digital twins will be a default augmentation for any EMI in the future. But for the PastModern Modular project we focus on some specific historical instruments, which usually existed in limited copies or in a single variant. To stress and explore possibility of spatial embodiment of VR - we focus furthermore on those instruments, which had unique spatial characteristics: they either were much bigger than modern EMIs, or required spatial interaction. These features (especially size) sometimes made them difficult to keep, maintain, recreate and market. But the same features make them

particularly interesting objects to try to put into VR space. We also would like to open this project for the non-electronic instruments, which were significant for developing the aesthetic of electronic music or modern music in general. Examples of these would be purely mechano-acoustic Intonarumory (built by Luigi Russolo and Ugo Piatti c.1910) and mechano-electric Free Music Machine (created by Percy Grainger & Burnett Cross c.1948), and some others.

2 Big Projects of the Past

Media archaeological research into the history of EMIs is active and far from being finalized. Here we briefly outline some of the instruments, which might be considered for the project just at the beginning of the early prototyping stage.

One of the criterias in this particular collection - is a spatial curiosity of the instrument. We consider it spatially curious, if it is either drastically different in size from modern market EMIs, or requires specific spatial interactions. Another criteria - relative simplicity of modeling on this early stage of prototyping (also keeping in mind the LOD approach).

Due to limitations for the size of the paper we can not provide descriptions for the instruments. A great channel of information on the topic of historical EMIs is a web-site by Simon Crab et al., called "120 Years of Electronic Music" (www.120years.net), which in a lot of cases served as a primary resource for this very short review. We organize the examples chronologically, and whoever is interested in their descriptions can find the information online.

Telharmonium c.1896

Intonarumori c.1913

Theremin c.1918

Termen's Keyboard Electric Harmonium c.1926

Terpsitone c.1932

Free Music Machine c.1948

ANS c.1957

RCA Mark II Sound Synthesizer c.1957

Hands c.1984

Radio Baton c.1989

3 Practical Proof of Concept

3.1 Technical Premise: procedural audio in virtual environments

The rise of accessible game creation tools like Unity3D and Unreal Engine (UE) has simplified VR environment development. However, while 3D modeling and interaction design for visuals have thrived, interactive audio has been neglected. Until recently, integrated and tested interactive audio tools for VR creation were lacking. Implementing real-time audio reactions in VR environments requires complex DSP operations, known as procedural audio generation. Without procedural audio, VR musical instruments (VRMIs) are severely limited.

Currently there are many possible ways of working with procedural audio. From a recently released Metasounds system for UE, to writing custom plugins for Wwise (a sound design platform for computer games). Due to limitations to the size of this paper, we can not describe even some of them.

For the practical part of our project we used a LibPD wrapper for Unity. It integrates PD (Pure Data) patches as embedded code, providing a simple implementation for non-coders. Unfortunately, it's no longer maintained, posing a challenge for future use unless revived by other developers. But for the purpose of rapid prototypes it still can be used. We've been introduced to this workflow at the workshop "Prototyping NIMEs in VR", conducted by Anil Çamcı and John Granzow at NIME 2023 conference (Çamcı 2023).

3.2 LOD (Level Of Detail) methodology

As mentioned earlier, we use a technical term LOD (level of detail), acquired from Unity engine (see Fig.4) as a metaphor to structure the variety of possible representations of our project. What we propose here - is a qualitative scale, which can be used for soft formalization.

Fig. 4. LOD 0 - the model is closest to the camera and has the largest number of parts. LOD 1 - the model is further from the camera and the number of details (polygons) is fewer. (source: Unity 2024)

We can suggest that the digital twin of the music instrument in “LOD 0” should have the largest number of details possible and also have as close interaction and sound to the physical twin as it can get. Practically, it is probably not possible to reach this level at this point of our technical resources. “LOD 0” can be perceived as an ideal digital twin. At the same time we can put an arbitrary good level of detailing as “LOD x”. Then any implementation which will have more details than “LOD x” can be marked as “LOD<x”. And any, which will be lower in detail can be indexed as “LOD>x”.

LOD 0 - the ideal digital twin of the instrument. Visual, interactive and sonic aspects are almost indistinguishable from the physical twin.

LOD x - a good implementation of the digital twin on the currently available level of technological basis. Visuals have custom textures and shaders. Sound is purely procedural and modeled based on the analysis of the generation in the physical twin. IKC - which is “Interactive Kinematic Concept” in terms from (Kasich 2023) - is as close to the physical twin as allowed by the VR controllers used.

LOD>x - a convenient implementation, which can be used as proof of concept or an illustrative prototype. Visuals can be schematic and have default textures. Sound may have procedural elements, but also may use audio samples. IKC can be implemented partly, or speculative or purely illustrative.

We suggest using different levels of LOD in a non-hierarchical fashion, similar to how it is done in the MEMI (Morphological Evolution of Music Interface) paradigm (Kasich 2023). Which means any digital twin on any level of LOD - can be seen and used as a full fledged music instrument on its own.

3.3 Building LOD>x digital twin for the Theremin c.1918

This digital twin was implemented with the LibPD wrapper for Unity game engine (described above). We used META Quest 2 as a VR\XR input-output interface.

Visuals:

The 3D model of the Theremin was sketched, using primitives inside the Unity itself (Fig.5). We adjusted the size to be similar to one of the early models of Theremin, available on the archival photographs.

Fig. 5. Left: Lev Termen with one of the early Theremins in 1932 (source Ria Novosti, taken from (Crab 2024)). Center and Right: LOD>x Theremin 3D model built with Unity primitives.

Sound:

Audio is purely procedural. It was programmed as a patch in Pure Data with one oscillator and two variables to control pitch and volume (Fig.6). As this is the LOD>x twin - we do not try the physical modeling of the original Theremin schematics.

Fig. 6. The PD patch for the LOD>x Theremin digital twin: two variables input.

IKC:

The interaction is close to the original Theremin, to as much as currently used VR controllers allow us to, except one detail - before the performance a player must grab two grabbable boxes, which serve as “virtual fists”. The custom C# script measures distances from the boxes to the dedicated antennas, returning the variables for calculations of pitch and volume. The closer the right fist to the right (vertical) antenna - the higher the pitch. The closer the left fist to the left (horizontal) antenna - the lower the volume (Fig.7 & Fig.8).

We are aware of two main techniques of Theremin performance: “the fist technique” (articulating sound with fists) and “the finger technique” (playing with short-distance finger gestures). In this LOD>x twin we only implement the first one.

Fig.7. View from inside VR: left - start position; center - check pitch antenna; right - check volume antenna.

Fig.8. Combined view during a performance: center - from inside the helmet; upper right - performer in the physical world.

3.4 Building LOD>x digital twin for the Keyboard Electric Harmonium c.1926

Using the same technique as above we assemble a very basic digital twin for the last version of Electric Harmonium.

Visuals:

The 3D model was sketched with Unity primitives and the keys and rotating dials were taken from the XR-Interaction-Toolkit examples (Unity 2024).

Fig. 9. Left: last version of the Keyboard Harmonium (source (Kavina 2024)). Center and Right: LOD>x Keyboard Harmonium 3D model built with Unity primitives and example XR UI elements (dials and keys).

Sound:

Again the audio is purely procedural. Without doing any research on actual schematics of the instrument, which would be done for the LOD<x digital twin, we just use a simple oscillator for each key. And the dial controls the pitch. Maybe a peculiar part here is the spatialisation fix, which is used to locate the virtual sound sources into the virtual speaker objects (the white ovals in Fig.9). In the case of Theremin, we have rendered sound universally - that is it was not spatial and just played mono directly to output. As discussed above - a unique feature of the last Harmonium version - is that each key has its dedicated speaker positioned on a plain array above the keys and dials. That is what we model here quite precisely. In fact the player in the VR helmet can position their head in different parts of the virtual speaker panel to listen to alternated volumes. The spatial fix is specific for the LibPD integration we use for this prototyping and can be found in tutorials (Moody et al.).

Fig. 10. The PD patch for the isolated generator of LOD>x Harmonium digital twin with spatial audio fix seen in the patch as the input object [adc~] modulating the main audio signal.

IKC:

The interaction here is not very precise in the part of keys. And this so far will be the issue with all keys and buttons, because using META Quest 2 we are not capable of tracking fingers. We also use 3D models, which do not represent piano keys, used in the original Harmonium. The dial interaction though may be considered close enough to the original. It is a 360 rotation, which follows the rotation of the wrist with a hand controller (see Fig.11). We use custom C# scripts to withdraw the values from the virtual keys and dials and translate them to our sound generating system.

Fig. 11. A sequence from left to right showing a virtual dial rotation following right hand wrist rotation. This changes the pitch of the specific generator, while the key is pressed (by the left hand) exactly like in a physical Harmonium.

3.5 Implying modularity with mereotopological calculus

As we discussed earlier, modularity is an implicit feature of digital twins (Rosen 2015). Now when we have even such simple LOD>x examples, we can analyze them mereologically. Below you can see a mereological dissection of the LOD>x Theremin and it's mereotopological transformation (Fig.12).

Fig. 12. From left to right: first two pictures are mereological dissection of the LOD>x Theremin twin (we see the parts); next two are a mereotopological transformation (we change the color and merge two parts)

It is important to note, that besides their spatial reassembly - the function of the parts persists. We follow the further transformations (Fig.13).

Fig. 13. Further transformations from left to right: multiplication, spatial merging.

We call these transformations mereotopological, because they obey some spatial logic. It is something similar to Region Based Calculus (Stell 2017): we see multiplication and merging (which is a form of summation). And these operations are applicable on different parts of every object to as far as you can dissect. Which is obvious for simulated 3D objects in VR. The important thing for us, is that the objects, with which we operate - are historical music instruments (or their interactive twins). Below you can see, that mereotopologically

transformed LOD>x Theremin is fully operational interactive music instrument and it continues to follow the logic of the parts of the original Theremin (Fig 14).

Fig. 14. Transformed twin remains interactive and follows the logic of parts of the physical twin: a purple antenna controls volume, a green - pitch, every two antennas control one oscillator. But now due to spatial transformation - IKC is changing. It is a new instrument, “modulated” from Theremin by multiplication and summation of LOD>x twins.

As we see, the parts of the Theremin twin can be considered as modules. Hence modularity. The Harmonium twin also consists of modules. In fact it is a multiplied module itself. We can assemble different modular systems with modules of Theremin and Harmonium (see Fig.15). And of course the main feature would be the intermodulation of controls and signal-flows. For example we can map one Theremin antenna to control a row of buttons and another to control selected pitch-dials, and another one to control the movement of Harmonium speakers in space. Anything is possible in VR. That is why our project has a conceptual basis - digital twins of historical instruments. It serves as a limitation and provides a set of rules, or constraints, or we can call it a lexicon, or a calculus.

Fig. 14. Anything possible in VR. E.g. several Theremin antennas control different parameters of Harmonium modules: like several buttons or a set of dials, or a spatial arrangement of speakers.

We would not dare to take more time from the reader and start describing possibilities of audio-signal modulations, especially that they were not practically implemented in this prototype, besides obvious mixing artifacts, like beatings and so on. We leave it for further research.

4 Modularity of Higher Degrees of Freedom - Play Together Forever

In this final part we are going to speculate on the further developments of this project. First and obvious one would be to try to reach a state, where several LODx level twins would be present within one system, and be able to work as a library of modules. The next steps would require constant improvement of modeling and scripting, updating of audio generation systems and gameplay according to the advancement of technologies. And also adding new models to the library. It is a huge work on its own. But it is very much obvious. It is more interesting to think about the affordances of VRMIs within our paradigm. In our mereotopological calculus we establish the rules. For example we willfully decide, that we shall keep dissected parts of the instrument static or adherent to a certain shape. For sure we can loosen the rules and give higher degrees of freedom to the project. For example, we can say that every time two antennas present in the scene - we have a Theremin. And we can add that the antennas do not have to be of a specific shape (Fig.15).

Fig. 15. Screenshots of a gameplay of a scene, where we have three Theremins in a form of blue fields with columns taller than the average human and every cube controls one of the three different tembras. This is a simple interactive prototype, built using the same workflow as described earlier.

Another example of such an approach has been shown in an old work by Sergey Kasich (Kasich 2014), performed live at the CTM festival in Berlin. The author sampled waveforms from the recordings of a historical photo-optic synthesizer Variophone (built by Evgeniy Sholpo in 1932), digitized the photos of oscillator glass wheels of the instrument, and combined everything inside the virtual environment into a surreal interactive landscape. The player would jump into the huge optical oscillator wheel, which would grow into a brutalist architectural structure and start rotating. Every time the blocks would pass through or near the player - they would hear one period of the original Variophone's waveform. The rotation would create a periodic wave. This would be the closest experience of being inside the working photo-optic oscillator. And this is an example of LOD>x digital twin in a fashion of PastModern Modular with high degrees of freedom (Fig.16).

Fig. 16. Screenshots of a gameplay of VAR_3D performance at CTM 2014. From upper left to lower left and from upper right to lower right: a sequence of jumping into the Variophone's photo-optic oscillator, where the architectural structure grows, in which every block is one period of the original waveform of the historical instrument. The structure starts rotation, while the player-listener can freely move inside it, experiencing formation of a waveform from separate periods binaurally (source (Kasich 2014)).

Now let's go very far with this and discuss Michael Jackson. Is he really dead?

Fig. 17. JACKO CHAMBER Michael Jackson's oxygen chamber where he took naps so he could live 'forever' found in shipping container 10 years after his death (source The SUN, 30 June 2019)

In (Fig.17) we can see Michael Jackson in his alleged attempt to live forever (or very long). But we would argue that the oxygen camera did not help to reach the purpose. Much more useful happened to be the huge number of digitally recorded and stored data about Michael. Especially how he looked, how he moved in 3D space and how he sounded. These aspects were the selling points of him as a commercial enterprise, and that is why we have a lot of information about them. Having all this data, it is possible to build numerous digital twins of various LODs for Michael Jackson. And sure enough it has been successfully done and will continue (Fig.18).

Fig. 18. Upper left: Michael Jackson (officially dead in 2009) performs onstage (as a hologram) during the 2014 Billboard Music Awards at the MGM Grand Garden Arena on May 18, 2014 in Las Vegas, Nevada (source Billboard). Upper right: LODx digital twin of Michael in the form of a high resolution 3D model (copyright Amin Vanaki). Lower: a sequence showing a characteristic Jackson's dance loop stored in a form of interactive animations of a rigged 3D model (copyright Brandon Waggoner).

In our case it means, that anyone, who has left some sort of retractable recording of performance with any of the historical music instruments - can play them again and potentially forever. As long as the person can be restored as a digital twin and put into the same VR space, as the digital twins of the instruments. Examples can be digital twins of Lev Termen, performing early Theremin along with you as a user of your own digital twin system. Or Michel Waisvisz playing with his Hands interface, modulating the performance

of Max Mathews with Radio Baton and Lavinia Williams with Therpsitone. Hypothetically we all can be copied into VR and play our instruments together forever.

One of the assemblies of a PastModern Modular system with high degrees of freedom, though limited to one performer, is illustrated in (Fig.19).

Fig. 19. Sketch of the PastModern Modular with high degrees of freedom: red - performer; green - a trace of movement, which becomes a graphic score; blue - direction of the score, where to the left it becomes glass and is read by ANS generators, to the right it becomes paper and is read by Free Music Machine generator; purple - different modules.

5 Conclusion: not old, just different

Our paper describes a project, which has two main goals. One is preservation of cultural heritage and potential opening of it to a larger public through a unified standardized format of representation - digital twin or a VRMI (Virtual Reality Music Instrument). Another goal - trying to consider the historical instruments as a library of modules, which could be part of a modular system. That system might be useful for modern music creation as a peculiar explorative tool and at the same time a music instrument on its own. We have provided a

conceptual basis for these two narratives and showed the technical possibility of such development through a functional proof of concept design. In the end we showed possibilities of adding more degrees of freedom to the project and looped the topic of time travel with the idea of eternal life.

We conclude with the note that the two goals are important to be followed together. Modularity adds a creative and vital aspect to the preserved technology. And the basis in cultural heritage and history guarantees a set of conceptual limitations to the modular system, without which it may become just another trivial speculative software synthesizer. This combination becomes possible with the flexibility of digitally mediated Virtual Reality, where time and space can be questioned. If the progress of human culture continues to advance digitalization, perhaps we will reconsider all time-related scales. Readers may notice that while discussing historical instruments, we tried to avoid using the word "old".

In the world of alternative timings nothing is old - it is just different.

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